

(THF) at 308.15 K. In this note excess volumes for the same systems at 303.15 K and 313.15 K are reported to calculate temperature coefficient $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$.

Experimental and Results

The apparatus, procedure and materials for these measurements have been described earlier⁴. A Lipkin type⁵ bicapillary pycnometer have been used for the measurement of density. The density data are correct to 0.0001.

The excess volumes V^E were calculated from the density data at 303.15 K and 313.15 K over entire range of composition from 0 to 1 for all the three systems using following relation (1).

$$V^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/d_{12} - (M_1x_1/d_1 + M_2x_2/d_2) \quad \dots (1)$$

where M, x and d represent molecular weight, mole fraction and density respectively. Subscripts 1, 2 and 12 refer to the pure components and the mixture respectively. The excess volume V^E so obtained are graphically represented in Fig. 1 for all the three systems at both the temperatures 303.15 K and 313.15 K. There is an increase in excess volume with the increase in the temperature. The excess volumes and temperature coefficient $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$ at $x_1 = x_2 = 0.5$ are listed in Table 1. The excess volumes are negative and the temperature coefficients $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$ are positive in every case.

Fig. 1. Excess volumes for three binary solutions of m-, o-, and p-xylenes in tetrahydrofuran. x_2 is the mole fraction of tetrahydrofuran.

- (a) m-xylene+THF : $\circ-\circ-\circ$ 303.15 K
 $\bullet-\bullet-\bullet$ 313.15 K
- (b) o-xylene+THF : $\triangle-\triangle-\triangle$ 303.15 K
 $\blacktriangle-\blacktriangle-\blacktriangle$ 313.15 K
- (c) p-xylene+THF : $\square-\square-\square$ 303.15 K
 $\blacksquare-\blacksquare-\blacksquare$ 313.15 K

TABLE 1—EXCESS VOLUME V^E AND TEMPERATURE COEFFICIENT $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$ at $x_1 = x_2 = 0.5$

Systems	temp.	V^E cm ³ mole ⁻¹	$(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$ cm ³ mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹
m-xylene+THF	303.15 K	-0.263	0.0012
	308.15 K	-0.258 ^a	
	313.15 K	-0.251	
o-xylene+THF	303.15 K	-0.285	0.0005
	308.15 K	-0.282 ^a	
	313.15 K	-0.280	
p-xylene+THF	303.15 K	-0.330	0.0048
	308.15 K	-0.310 ^a	
	303.15 K	-0.282	

a. ref. 4.

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Salting of Naphthols

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INTRODUCTION of neutral salts into the aqueous phase increases the partition coefficients of organic solutes between organic solvents and water¹. The phenomenon depends on the influence of the salts on water structure. In salt solutions which are known to be structure breakers, the trend is toward salting-out. Several theoretical approaches²⁻⁸ have been used with varying degrees of success. In salt solutions of polar nonelectrolyte solutes, the molecular interactions are more complex and the pattern of solubility behaviour is less readily predictable.

The present work is concerned with the salting-out studies on α - and β -naphthols. The naphthol activity coefficients, standard free energy, enthalpy and entropy of transfer from water to the salt solutions have been evaluated.

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Experimental

Cyclohexane, naphthols and the salts were of pure grade, E. Merck or B. D. H. and used as such. The naphthols were equilibrated at a fixed concentration ($10^{-3}M$) between equal volumes of cyclohexane and different salt solutions ranging from 0.2 M to 2.0 M in a thermostatic shaker at 20, 30 and 40° ($\pm 0.2^\circ$). The aqueous layers and the organic layers were separated at equilibrium and estimated spectrophotometrically in a Carl Zeiss Specord UV-Visible Spectrophotometer. The absorbances were noted at the near UV peak 295 nm for α -naphthol and at 330 nm for β -naphthol where Beer-Lambert law is found to be valid. The distribution coefficients of the naphthols between cyclohexane and water and cyclohexane and various salt solutions were calculated and utilized for computation of solute activity coefficients and transfer thermodynamic quantities.

Results and Discussion

The activity coefficient of a nonelectrolyte f_N may be expressed as a function of the electrolyte and nonelectrolyte concentrations C_s and C_N at a given temperature⁹.

$$\log f_N = K_s C_s + K_1 C_N$$

where K_s is the salting or ion-nonelectrolyte interaction parameter and K_1 is the self-interaction parameter. When C_N is much lower than C_s the self-interaction term is neglected.

If for two experiments in the distribution of a nonelectrolyte between aqueous solutions and an immiscible nonaqueous reference phase, one involving pure water and the other a salt solution, the concentration of nonelectrolyte in the reference phase is constant, we can write

$$\frac{f_N}{f_N^0} = (C_N^0/C_N) = (K_s \cdot C_{org}) / (K_w \cdot C'_{org})$$

where K_s = partition coefficient of the solute between organic phase and salt solution of concentration C_s , K_w = partition coefficient of the solute between the organic phase and water, C'_{org} = solute concentration in the organic phase in the experiment with the salt solution and C_{org} = solute concentration in the organic phase in the experiment with pure water.

The distribution coefficients of both α - and β -naphthols increase from water to salt solution in the order $Na_2SO_4 > NaCl > NaClO_4$. On the contrary, measurements with KSCN show a decrease in the partition coefficient. The salting coefficients K_s , were obtained from the relationship

$$K_s = \lim_{C_s \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{d \log f/f_0}{d C_s} \right)$$

The plot of $\log f/f_0$ against C_s gave straight lines as shown in Fig. 1. The values of K_s were calculated from the slopes. These are listed in Table 1 at 20° only. The Setschenow equation¹⁰, $\log f/f_0 = K_s C_s$, was precisely applicable to these systems. Negative K_s in the case of KSCN shows salting-in. As is evident from Fig. 1, the K_s values for β -naphthol are in general less than those of α -naphthol. The decreasing order of K_s values $Na_2SO_4 > NaCl > NaClO_4 > KSCN$ tallies with the salting order for a number of solutes of widely varying chemical nature¹. This is also in agreement with the relative influence of ions on water structure¹¹.

Fig. 1. The plot of $\log f/f_0$ vs salt concentration for α - and β -naphthol at 298K. Straight lines drawn by the method of least squares.

The standard free energy of transfer of a mole of naphthol from pure water to a salt solution C_s is calculated from the equation

$$\Delta G_{tr} = RT \frac{d \ln f/f_0}{d C_s} = 2.303 RT \cdot K_s$$

TABLE 1— K_s VALUES AND TRANSFER THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES AT 20°; ΔG_{tr} , ΔH_{tr} IN cal mole⁻¹ AND ΔS_{tr} IN cal mole⁻¹ deg⁻¹

Salt	α -naphthol				β -naphthol			
	K_s	ΔG_{tr}	$-\Delta H_{tr}$	$-\Delta S_{tr}$	K_s	ΔG_{tr}	$-\Delta H_{tr}$	$-\Delta S_{tr}$
Na_2SO_4	0.472 ± 0.007	682.8	330.0	3.3	0.398 ± 0.001	526.9	69.0	2.0
NaCl	0.197 ± 0.001	264.1	333.3	2.0	0.144 ± 0.006	193.1	98.9	0.8
$NaClO_4$	0.081 ± 0.002	108.6	67.1	0.6	0.080 ± 0.003	107.3	170.7	0.95
KSCN	-0.018 ± 0.001	-24.1	68.6	0.15	-0.036 ± 0.002	-48.3	77.6	0.1

The enthalpy of transfer ΔH_{tr} is calculated from the slopes of plots between the K_s values and the inverse of absolute temperatures for different salts. The entropy of transfer ΔS_{tr} is calculated from the relationship

$$-\Delta S_{tr} = RT \frac{d(\ln f/f_0)}{dT} + R(\ln f/f_0)$$

The values of ΔG_{tr} , ΔH_{tr} and ΔS_{tr} at 20° are also listed in Table 1.

Experimental results indicate that K_s is a function of salt concentration as also of the distribution ratio of the solute in aqueous and organic phases. The geometry and the polarity of the molecules also induce salt-naphthol specific interactions^{1,2,13} which in turn modifies the ionic influences on the water structure. It is well known that α -hydroxyl group in naphthalene is more reactive than the β -hydroxyl. This may lead to several enhanced interactions, viz. aggregation of α -naphthol in the organic phase and solvation of α -naphthol in the aqueous phase while salt-naphthol interactions may be reduced. Correcting for the concentration dependence of K_w , the solute dimerization constants in cyclohexane are found to be 603.5 for α -naphthol and 567.1 for β -naphthol. When similar modifications are extended to K_s values for cyclohexane-naphthol-salt solution systems, the trend persists. Interestingly however, the trend is reversed when the salt is KSCN. The $\log f/f_0$ and ΔG_{tr} values of the naphthols clearly reflect the interplay of all these effects.

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Synthesis and Bromination of 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl) chromone

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LITERATURE shows that no work on the bromination of 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone has been done. Further a large number of flavones¹⁻⁵ have been reported to possess antimicrobial activity. It was, therefore, considered of interest to study the synthesis and bromination of 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone.

2'-Hydroxy phenyl-6-methoxy-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone gave a yellow needle shaped compound m.p. 270° when heated with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol for 16 hrs. The compound did not give violet colouration with ferric chloride. Infrared spectra of the compound in nujol mulls showed a band at 1635 cm^{-1} due to carbonyl group⁶. Therefore, 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone structure was assigned to it. The same compound was also prepared by debromination of 2'-hydroxy phenyl- α - β -dibromo- β -2-methoxy-1-naphthyl ethyl ketone⁷. Wheeler *et al*⁷ prepared this flavone and reported m.p. 178°.

With one or three moles of bromine in acetic acid 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone yielded a dibromo derivative which on alkaline hydrolysis gave the known 3,5-dibromo-salicylic acid. The dibromo flavone showed an infrared band at 1660 cm^{-1} due to carbonyl group⁶. 6,8-Dibromo-2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone structure was therefore assigned to it.

Experimental

2-(2'-Methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone : 2'-Hydroxy phenyl-6-methoxy-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone (1 g), selenium dioxide (1.5 g) and amyl alcohol (15 ml) were refluxed on a oil bath at 135 to 145° for 16 hrs. A yellow product was obtained on cooling which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave golden yellow needles (0.6 g) m.p. 270° (Found : C, 78.98 ; H, 4.17. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 79.47 ; H, 4.63%).

2-Hydroxy phenyl- α - β -dibromo- β -2-methoxy-1-naphthyl ethyl ketone (1 g) was taken in acetic acid (15 ml) and potassium hydroxide (1 g) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on wire gauze for 8 hrs. The product separating on cooling was crystallised from glacial acetic acid. M.P. and mixed m.p. with the product described above was 207°.

6,8-Dibromo-2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone : 2-(2'-Methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone (0.302 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (15 ml) and bromine in acetic acid (10%, 5.4 ml) added to it. The reaction